
The Importance of English Language For the Educational Skills

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***Annotation.** English language plays an essential role in our lives as it helps in communication. It is the main language for studying any subject all over the world. English is important for students as it broadens their minds, develops emotional skills, improve the quality of life by providing job opportunities.*

***Keywords:** English language, teachers, skills, ability, translating.*

INTRODUCTION

Why Learning English language is important?

- **Perfect communication** – It is important to speak effectively. People get impressed by those who have good communication skills.
 - **Gain Confidence** – If you own good communication skills then your confidence will automatically be high.
 - **Achieve your goal early** – Effective English language skills help you meet your career goals quickly.
 - **Effective personality** – When we speak effectively and with confidence, anyone can get attracted.
 - **Part of the Global community** – English language is a part of the global world. So, if one knows good English then one can interact with others.
 - **Multiple Career Prospects** – A person possessing effective communication skills have more career opportunities than others.
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How to improve your English language skills?

There are various ways of improving English language skills, we discuss a few of them.

- Learn ten new words on a daily basis.
- Try to speak in English with friends and family members.
- Make a list of daily used items in English and try to use them on a regular basis.
- Watch English news channels, movies, serials, etc. and try to understand them.
- Read English Magazines, newspapers, novels, etc. The word you find tough underline and find its meaning in the dictionary.
- Participate in group discussions, this will give you confidence.
- Try to make notes on daily the basis or start writing a diary.
- Practice speaking skills for 5 minutes daily in front of the mirror.
- Practice grammar exercises of noun, verbs, adverbs, idioms, etc.
- Start thinking in English and write stories to improve both speaking and writing skills.
- Never feel shy while speaking, no one is perfect. One can learn only by speaking.
- Make friends who are native English speakers, it will help you a lot in learning English language skills.

The importance of the English language is wider in education. A student studies other subjects in the English language only like Science, Economics, Geography, History etc. if he knows the general rules of grammar well then the student can easily write the notes and ace in exams.

Language lab software is used to learn English skills easily. Digital language lab consists of a huge content to learn English language skills. It is an innovative step towards learning a language in an effective way. It is an easy way of learning a language and brings a change in personality. As we all know, communication skills are very important to communicate with other persons and make them understand what we want or what message we want to convey to them.

The benefits of English language lab software

Based on LSRW (listening, speaking, reading and writing) skills.

It is used in schools, colleges, universities, corporate, etc.

It is a useful tool for classroom engagement and interaction.

It overcomes the traditional teaching system.

It promotes the interactive learning process.

Soft skills are also taught in the language lab system.

Any foreign language could be learned with the help of language lab software.

With the growing competition, it has become essential to speak and write English perfectly. English language system is a perfect solution for learning the English language, it has levels from beginner to advance. It depends upon the learner from which level he wants to learn. The software is user-friendly and has soft skill courses that will polish your skills and give you the confidence to face the world.

English Language lab software provides technical tools for students to learn the pronunciation of language in an easy way. It also helps in learning the basic skills of the English language. Students learn in an easy way through interactive videos.

Some of the features of language lab software are:

It develops communication skills in students.

It facilitates teachers with real-time monitoring.

It builds confidence in learners.

It is a user-friendly software

It helps to improve pronunciation.

It helps in grooming overall personality.

It is an effective way of learning any language.

It removes the fear and hesitation of students.

English is not our native language, so why many students feel hard to learn English skills effectively. But with regular practice and adopting the various techniques given above will help you in learning English skills easily. Not only this, one will feel more confident when one can understand the English language and communicate with others without feeling hesitant.

Various language lab software is available in the market or we can say there are different types of language software present but among them Spears language lab is best for learning English language skills, as it has huge multimedia-based content for learning as well as practicing exercises. The detail of the content is given below:

Vocabulary – A language lab consists of 5000+ words for the students to learn and improve their speaking and writing skills.

Grammar – The grammar part consists of spot the error, idioms, synonyms, antonyms, one-word substitute and many other lessons to practice and gain grammar knowledge.

Accent training facility – Language lab system also has the feature of accent training in three languages Indian, British and American.

Intonation – This feature helps in improving the knowledge of the English language by knowing the variation of pitch, volume, speed, and stress of voice.

Phonetics – It is the study of speech sounds. The accent of different words made easy with phonetics. They help us to pronounce a word in the correct way.

Pronunciation – Learning how to pronounce a word is very important in the English language. If the pronunciation is correct, the end-user can easily understand your message and reply back.

MTI (Mother Tongue Influence) – Many times we have seen that when people talk in the English language we can judge their mother tongue, due to the influence of it. MTI technique is very beneficial in removing this influence.

Pace of speech – Pace is the key to effective communication in which speech is clearly understood. The pace of speech should remain constant, not high or low. In language lab software you can test your pace of speech with the help of a graph given in the voice recording feature.

Fluency – In order to improve fluency one can practice the application based on intonation and modulation. The regular practice will improve the fluency and brings confidence in the user.

ASL (Assessment of speaking and listening skills) – This feature of assessment of speaking and listening skills helps in better communication and check learner's proficiency.

Speech sounds – Pronunciation of consonants and vowel sounds made easy with correct syllabic division and stress patterns.

Soft Skills – Spears language lab software also covers soft skills like personality development, resume writing, group discussion, interview skills and many more to enhance the overall personality of the learners. These courses will bring confidence in the user and help in overcoming the fear of speaking in public.

Hence, with the help of English language lab software and by regular practice students can improve their English language in short duration. Students have very well understood the importance of English in their lives. If students start learning from an early age then it will be very easy for them to grab the things and memorize the concepts. No one can help them until they start helping themselves. So, it is better to start early then be late in understanding the basics of English language.

References:

1. John L. Douglas, The Role of a Banking System in Nation-Building, 60 Me. L. Rev. 511 (2008).
2. Gulmira, T., Sobirov, B., Suyunovich, T. I., & Hasanovna, A. D. Implementation Of Up-To-Date Innovative Approaches In A Competitive Merit Of Tourism Industry In Central Asia. The Case Of Uzbekistan. Journal of Management Value & Ethics, 4.
3. Gulmira, T., Sobirov, B., Suyunovich, T. I., & Hasanovna, A. D. Implementation Of Up-To-Date Innovative Approaches In A Competitive Merit Of Tourism Industry In Central Asia. The Case Of Uzbekistan. Journal of Management Value & Ethics, 4.
4. Tukhliev, I. S., Hayitboev, R., Safarov, B. S., & Tursunova, G. R. (2014). Basics of tourism. Textbook. Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.- T.:". Science and technology, 151.
5. Тухлиев, И. С., Бабаев, Ф., & Махмудова, А. (2017). Основные задачи дальнейшего развития туристической отрасли Узбекистана. Индустрия туризма: возможности, приоритеты, проблемы и перспективы, 10(1), 391-398.
6. Болтабаев, М. Р., Тухлиев, И. С., Сафаров, Б. Ш., & Абдурахимов, С. А. (2018). Туризм: теория и практика. Т.: Fan va texnologiya.
7. Suyunovich, T. I., & Pirmamatovna, M. A. (2023). Use of Digital Technologies Is Becoming One of the Main Tasks of the Tourism Industry. Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal, 2(6), 134-137.
8. Sadibekova, B., Makhmudova, A., Abdukhamidov, S., & Mukhamadiev, A. (2021). The main forms of pilgrimage tourism. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE, 2 (2), 84-88.
9. Abdukhamidov, A. S., & Makhmudova, A. P. (2022). Prospects for the development of recreational tourism in Uzbekistan. Builders Of The Future, 2(02), 31-38.
10. Makhmudova, A. (2019). Enhancement of the Ecotourism Efficiency in the Republic of Uzbekistan: Experience of the Developed Countries. Indonesian Journal of Law and Economics Review, 3, 10-21070.
11. Makhmudova, A. (2020). Organizational and economic reasons preventing the development of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan. Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems, 12(6), 1217-1220.

- 12.** Erkin, G., & Odilov, A. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(10), 412-416.
- 13.** Elena, S. (2023). Importance of Events for Tourism Management. *Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress*, 2(4), 119-123.
- 14.** Erkayeva, G., & Vayskulov, R. (2022). Mintaqaviy turizmni rivojlanitirishda geoaxborot texnologiyalarning ahamiyat.“. Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion texnologiyalar”(Economics and Innovative Technologies) ilmiy elektron jurnali, 1, 344-352.
- 15.** Erkayeva, G., & Vayskulov, R. (2022). TURIZM SALOHIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MOBIL INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO‘LLARI. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 10(5), 348-356.
- 16.** Fayzullaevich, K. G., Panjiyevna, E. G., & Gaybulla o‘g‘li, F. K. (2021). LABOR MOTIVATION IN SMALL BUSINESS ENTERPRISES. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4(2), 89-93.